

An SDN QoE Monitoring Framework for VoIP and video applications

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Abstract—Over the past years there has been a rapid rise of the mobile communications industry which, combined with the limitations of the current communications networks' structure, necessitates the development of new networks with increased capabilities, so that users can be served with optimal quality of service and network resources utilization. Software Defined Networking (SDN) is a networking approach which transforms the network elements to simple forwarding devices, making decisions centrally. The quality of service perceived by the user, or Quality of Experience (QoE), is considered to be a matter of great importance in software defined networks. This paper presents the SDN QoE Monitoring Framework (SQMF), an SDN application that monitors and preserves the QoE for VoIP and video applications, by periodically monitoring various network parameters and using QoE estimation models.

Index Terms—Software defined networking, Quality of experience

I. INTRODUCTION

Lately, a drive for changing the conventional networking architecture and moving towards new networking paradigms is beginning to show. This trend can be explained by a number of factors related to the current state in computer systems networking, as well as to the emerging needs of next generation networks. The current networking state is characterized by the legacy technology which the majority of networks are built on. Despite their widespread adoption, traditional IP networks have severe disadvantages regarding optimization, capital costs, customization, configuration and vertical integration [1]. The main cause for these is the fact that networks are built using devices which have become exceedingly complex as they implement an ever-increasing number of distributed protocols and use closed and proprietary interfaces. Moreover, Cisco's latest report [2] shows an exponential increase in the number of mobile devices, which will continue in the forthcoming years. More and more users are seeking faster internet access, more advanced mobile phones, and generally direct communication with other people and access to information. There is quantified evidence that there is a rapid growth of data traffic over wireless networks and it will grow to 24.3 exabytes per month by 2019. Mobile data traffic will follow a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 57% from 2014 to 2019. In total, the global data traffic caused by new smart devices is projected to increase from 88% to 97% by 2019 [2]. The fifth generation wireless communication networks technology (5G) will arise to address the challenges which 4G systems are unable to face. Various targets are set

for the transmission rate metrics and constitute a challenge for 5G networks.

Software Defined Networking (SDN) is an emerging networking paradigm that promises to address the challenges occurring from the current networking state and the requirements of the future evolution. SDN breaks the vertical integration by separating the control logic (the control plane) from the underlying routers and switches that forward the traffic (the data plane), using an open standard protocol for the communication between them.

The importance of taking care of user satisfaction with service provisioning in SDNs has been realized. Content providers are immensely interested in ensuring a high degree of satisfaction for their end-users. Networks try to support the requirements based on Quality of Service (QoS) parameters, such as throughput, latency and jitter. However, the performance of a specific application cannot be determined by simply relying on QoS metrics [1]. Network level metrics traditionally used by network administrators are not adequate to indicate how satisfied a user is with his experience. Thus, the evaluation of network applications should be based on user-centric metrics that provide a better indication of the satisfaction of the end-users and define the Quality of Experience (QoE). QoE takes into consideration the end-to-end connection and applications that are currently running over that network connection and how multimedia elements are satisfying or meeting the end user's requirements.

Due to the significance of QoE provisioning in SDNs, there is a need for a complete SDN framework which can measure the QoE in the network in real time, immediately taking the necessary actions to preserve it at acceptable levels. It is important to be able to run applications in the network with the maximum QoE possible at all times, as well as improve it immediately and seamlessly in case of degradation. Such a framework is designed and presented in this paper under the name SQMF (SDN QoE Monitoring Framework). Its contribution goes into the real time QoE monitoring and preserving, using real QoE estimation models. SQMF measures some required metrics on the transmission path of a VoIP or video application, computes the path's QoE and changes the transmission path in case the QoE is lower than a threshold.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section II summarizes previous work in the field of measuring the QoE in SDN networks. In section III, the QoE estimation models used for this paper are described and our proposed approach, SQMF, is presented in detail. SQMF is experimentally evalu-

ated in section IV and finally, section V concludes this paper.

II. RELATED WORK

Many industrial and academic parties have been focusing their research activities on the concept of SDN. In particular, the QoE aspect of SDN has gained more and more attention over the past few years. This has resulted in the publication of several research papers, studies and solution proposals trying to provide approaches for user QoE enhancement aided by SDN, the most important of which are presented in this section.

The authors of [3] implement a QoS/QoE mapping and adjusting application, which can be used by an ISP to monitor users' QoE after having watched some video content and adjust it, if necessary. The framework obtains information from OpenFlow (OF) switches in the network as well as the score given by users after having watched the video and if an adjustment is needed, it is performed by calculating all possible paths to the users and transmitting the traffic via multiple paths.

Paper [4] proposes an SDN-based architecture which can be used to jointly optimize the multimedia flows' path assignment and the service utility measured as QoE. This is achieved by calculating the optimal and alternative sub-optimal service configurations and imposing the network paths that will meet the resource requirements of each service.

Another research work on QoE for SDNs is [5], which introduces a bandwidth management solution for multiple video streaming sessions by jointly optimizing bandwidth allocation and video rate selection. It adjusts the network bandwidth allocation and coordinate the video rate selections among the different streams.

Research work [6] focuses on the case of vehicular networks, where it is necessary to divide the network resources fairly among the vehicles connected to Road-Side Units (RSUs) in the network. The authors propose an SDN framework which classifies the vehicles to satisfied and unsatisfied, depending on whether each vehicle's QoE is kept above a threshold, and adjusts the transmission power of unsatisfied vehicles so that they connect to a new RSU with optimal signal level.

Another paper which examines multimedia transmission is [7]. A QoE- and context- aware SDN control plane approach is proposed, taking into consideration both QoS and QoE metrics. The QoE utility of each path is estimated, a primary and a fallback path are specified between source and destination and in case of congestion, their QoE utilities are re-estimated and an alleviation action is performed.

The current state-of-the-art approaches propose several QoE provisioning schemes for SDN networks, however they do not consider real time QoE evaluation with real QoE estimation models, which is our approach's contribution.

III. SQMF FRAMEWORK

This paper develops the SDN QoE Monitoring Framework (SQMF), an SDN framework implemented in order to overcome situations where the QoE can face degradation in an

SDN network, and preserve the QoE in VoIP and video applications. This is achieved by using an SDN Controller and implementing an additional module with extra functionality on top of it in order to monitor the topology links and measure statistics on them, estimate the QoE of the transmission path on *real time* and change the traffic's transmission path to an alternative one, when the QoE falls below a specified threshold.

A. Quality of Experience Estimation Models

In order to have an exact and unified measure of the QoE in various applications, several QoE models have been developed. Below are presented two QoE models, one for VoIP and one for video applications, which are used for SQMF's implementation.

a) *ITU-T G.107 E-model for VoIP* [8], [9]: Based on this model, the QoE for VoIP applications is given in relation to the transmission Rating factor R by the following relationship:

$$MOS = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } R < 0 \\ 1 + 0.035R + \\ + R(R - 60)(100 - R) & \\ 7 * 10^{-6}, & \text{if } 0 \geq R \geq 100 \\ 4.5, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where:

$$R = 94.2 - 0.024d - 0.11(d - 177.3)H(d - 177.3) - 11 - 40\ln(1 + 10p)$$

$$H(x) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } x < 0 \\ 1, & \text{if } x \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

for delay d and packet loss p .

b) *The ITU-T G.1070 E-model for video* [10]: Based on this model, the QoE for video applications is given by the following relationship:

$$MOS = 1 + I_{coding} * I_{transmission}$$

where MOS is the V_q parameter as expressed in [10] and:

$$I_{coding} = I_{Ofr} \exp\left\{-\frac{(\ln(F_{R_v}) - \ln(O_{fr}))^2}{2DF_{R_v}^2}\right\}$$

representing the video quality affected by the coding distortion and

$$I_{transmission} = \exp\left\{-\frac{P_{plv}}{D_{P_{plv}}}\right\}$$

representing the video quality affected by the transmission process.

If the video frame rate F_{r_v} , the video bit rate B_{r_v} and the video packet loss rate P_{plv} are known, the factors O_{fr} , I_{Ofr} , DF_{R_v} and $D_{P_{plv}}$ can be computed based on 12 coefficients as follows:

$$O_{fr} = v_1 + v_2 B_{r_v}$$

$$I_{Of_r} = v_3 - \frac{v_3}{1 + \frac{Br_v v_5}{v_4}}$$

$$DF_{R_v} = v_6 + v_7 Br_v$$

and

$$D_{P_{pl_v}} = v_{10} + v_{11} \exp\left\{\frac{-Fr_v}{v_8}\right\} + v_{12} \exp\left\{\frac{-Br_v}{v_9}\right\}$$

These coefficients depend on codec type, video format, key frame interval and video display size. Their default values for specific configurations may be found in [10] or may be derived using a standard methodology also provided in [10].

B. Proposed Approach

The approach which is used by SQMF in order to ensure that the QoE remains in satisfactory levels is the periodical link monitoring and QoE estimation based on paths' statistics and the traffic redirection in case of low QoE detection on the transmission path. The reference topology used for SQMF is depicted in Fig. 1. It consists of two hosts, h_1 and h_2 , which are connected through a main path, consisting of three switches (s_1 , s_9 and s_8) and a backup path, consisting of 8 switches (s_1 to s_8). The main path is chosen based on the number of hops between the two hosts.

Fig. 1. The SQMF implementation topology

The proposed approach is described by the following workflow: the application starts when the user (e.g. network administrator) provides the necessary input parameters, which are the source and destination node, the application type (VoIP or video) and a QoE threshold. Based on the input parameters, SQMF computes the shortest path between the source and destination hosts, which will be the main transmission path, as well as the second shortest path (if exists) which will assist as a backup path. Then, appropriate OpenFlow rules are inserted through SQMF to both the main and the backup paths' switches so that the traffic is forwarded to the next switch of the path and also statistics are sent to the SDN controller. Afterwards, the QoE monitoring process starts; the SDN controller periodically collects statistics from the switches (different statistics for each application type) and uses them to compute the QoE level. If the estimated value is lower

than the threshold specified as input, then appropriate rules are inserted dynamically to redirect traffic to the backup path. The workflow described above is illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. The SQMF workflow

The collected statistics for QoE estimation according to the streamed application type are:

- For VoIP applications, the *delay* and *packet loss* are necessary, in order to be able to use the G.107 E-model. Even though measurements on the application layer are preferred to accurately measure application performance, ISPs often do not have access to end-user devices and therefore use network layer measurements, which use infrastructure components to obtain statistics. This approach is not considered sufficient, as it lacks the ability to differ between different applications and traffic flows. In our proposed approach we use the fact that OF enabled switches and routers keep per-flow statistics to determine end-to-end network performance. OF's capabilities to inject packets in the network are used in order to compute the metrics.
 - Each time the SDN controller needs to measure the delay, it creates a packet with a specific source MAC address 00:00:00:00:00:09 in particular, injects it in each switch of the path and sends it to the output interface (except for the egress switch), so that the next switch of the path receives it. Each switch (except for the ingress switch, as it has no previous switch to receive a packet from) is configured with an appropriate flow rule to forward to the controller any packet with the specific MAC address. The difference between the time that a switch receives a packet and the time that the previous switch had sent the packet is the delay of a particular link. The addition of all the path links delays results in the path delay. Each switch is configured with a rule of the following format:

```
priority=1000,
dl_src=00:00:00:00:00:09,
actions=CONTROLLER:65535
```

- In order to compute the packet loss rate, and given that VoIP traffic generates UDP packets, the SDN controller periodically monitors the number of UDP packets sent from the sender (h_1) and the number of UDP packets received by the receiver (h_2) and computes their difference divided by the number of sent packets. To achieve packet loss monitoring, the ingress and the egress switches are configured appropriately so as to forward to the controller apart from the predefined output interface to the next node - any UDP packet they receive (the ingress receives UDP packets from the sender host and the egress from the previous path node). In its turn, the controller counts the paths total incoming and outgoing UDP packets and is able to determine the packet loss by computing their difference. The ingress and the egress switch are configured with rules of the following format:

```
priority=1000,udp,in_port=x,
actions=CONTROLLER:65535,output:y
```

For example, the appropriate rules for s_1 of Fig. 1 is:

```
priority=1000,udp,in_port=1,
actions=CONTROLLER:65535,output:3
```

and for s_8 is:

```
priority=1000,udp,in_port=3,
actions=CONTROLLER:65535,output:2
```

In cases where other sources of UDP traffic can be identified in the network as well, the VoIP traffic can be separated by extending the OpenFlow rule's match field with more information, for instance the source or destination IP address.

- For video applications, the *bit rate*, *frame rate* and *packet loss* are necessary, in order to use the G.1070 E-model.
 - The bit rate and the frame rate of the selected video are computed through the application. Specifically, in case the application type is specified as video in the input parameters, the video file for streaming is also specified. Therefore, SQMF locates the video file in the system and analyzes its properties, which leads to its bit rate and frame rate identification.
 - The packet loss is computed in the same way as for VoIP applications.

For both approaches, the implemented delay and packet loss computation method are based on the OpenNetMon framework, proposed in [11].

IV. EVALUATION

The current section conducts a proof-of-concept evaluation of SQMF through graphical representations that compare the networks behavior with and without the SQMF functionality in the event of a link failure, i.e. comparing the default forwarding with the QoE-based forwarding when a link failure

occurs. The SDN controller used is OpenDaylight Boron SR1. The framework was developed in Ubuntu 14.04 OS using Java 8 JDK, Maven 3.3.9 and IntelliJ IDE and extended the SDN Controller functionality by implementing an extra SDN module. The network topology used for validation and evaluation was created using the Mininet network emulator and is depicted in Fig. 1. The experiments were conducted both on VoIP and video traffic cases. For both types of traffic, as a first case, the SQMF functionality did not take place and therefore the packets kept being forwarded to the main path as initially configured when a link failure occurred. This caused total packet loss after the link failure.

Then, the same experiment was carried out using the SQMF functionality. In this case, the controller monitored periodically the QoE and when the QoE was detected to be lower than the threshold, due to the link failure, it efficiently changed the transmission path by configuring the packets to be forwarded to the backup path, so the packet losses were much lower.

- In order to evaluate the SQMF functionality for VoIP applications, VoIP traffic was generated from h_1 to h_2 for 105 seconds. The traffic was generated using the D-ITG traffic generator tool [12]. The parameters used for the current experiment are shown in Table I.

TABLE I
PARAMETERS USED FOR SQMF EVALUATION ON VOIP

Packets per second	50
VoIP codec	G.729.2

- In order to evaluate the SQMF functionality for video applications, video traffic was generated from h_1 to h_2 for 105 seconds. The traffic was generated using the VLC player. The parameters used for the current experiment are shown in the Table II and the coefficients derived by these parameters are shown in Table III.

TABLE II
PARAMETERS USED FOR SQMF EVALUATION ON VIDEO

Frame Rate	23.98 frames/sec
Bit Rate	1679000 bits/sec
Video Codec	H264
Video Format	VGA (640x480)
Video key frame interval	1

TABLE III
COEFFICIENTS DERIVED FROM PARAMETERS OF TABLE II

Coefficient	Value
v_1	5.517
v_2	0.0129
v_3	3.459
v_4	178.53
v_5	1.02
v_6	1.15
v_7	0.000355
v_8	0.114
v_9	513.77
v_{10}	0.736
v_{11}	-6.451
v_{12}	13.684

By illustrating the results of the two cases, with and without QoE monitoring, in the same graphical representation, it is obvious that QoE monitoring-based forwarding performs much better for video applications than the default forwarding to a configured main path for both VoIP and video traffic . Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 respectively show that QoE monitoring-based forwarding achieves much lower packet losses when a link failure occurs, managing to recover immediately after a small period of packet loss detection, in contrast to the default case where all the packets are lost after the link failure.

Fig. 3. Packet losses with and without SQMF for VoIP traffic

Fig. 4. QoE with and without SQMF for VoIP traffic

Therefore, the QoE monitoring-based forwarding implemented by SQMF preserves the total QoE and keeps it at high levels even after the link failure, whereas in the default case the QoE faces a permanent degradation after the failure for both VoIP and video traffic, as depicted in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 respectively.

Fig. 5. Packet losses with and without SQMF for video traffic.

Fig. 6. QoE with and without SQMF for video traffic.

V. CONCLUSION

The current networking state's limitations raise the need for an alternative approach to effectively face the challenges imposed. This alternative approach is SDN, which decouples the control from the data plane and transforms the network elements to simple forwarding devices, routing the traffic according to rules set to them by the control plane. A very important factor in the evaluation of SDN is the user's satisfaction from the service offered to him. To this end, this paper has developed an SDN framework for monitoring the QoE of VoIP and video applications in real-time that manages to preserve QoE at acceptable levels, despite sudden network problems, such as link failures. The implemented framework results in much lower packet losses than the default forwarding, and therefore to much higher QoE. This paper's contribution goes far beyond an abstract framework introduction, as it provides a practical implementation of real-time QoE monitoring in SDNs by using real QoE estimation models. Some interesting issues that have been identified as future work points are the following:

- The extension of SQMF to provide more than one backup paths, in case that the QoE is detected again low in the (first) backup path
- The experimentation with different kinds of network problems, not related to link failures (e.g. heavy congestion)
- The dynamic coefficients computation for the video QoE estimation model, so that the application can additionally deal with more challenging video types
- The integration of different QoE models into SQMF, related to other application types such as TCP-based video streaming, web browsing and IPTV, as well as to next-generation (5G) mobile networks, e.g. [13].

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